

and 0.25 kg ai/ha for penycyuron.

Disease incidence was assessed at harvest as follows:

$$\text{Disease incidence} = \frac{1(H) + 2(L) + 3(M) - 4(S_1) + 5(S_2)}{\text{Total no. of tillers}}$$

H = healthy tillers, L = lightly infected

tillers, M = moderately infected tillers, S₁ = severely infected tillers, and S₂ = very severely infected tillers (flag leaf dried and killed).

Of fungicides tested in PDA medium, inhibitory zones were shown only with triphenyltin hydroxide at 10 ppm and

penycyuron at 30 ppm.

Disease incidence and yield in two seasons are given in the table. In both seasons, the lowest disease incidence was with penycyuron applied 24 h after inoculation. □

Damage by rice root-knot nematode

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Healthy seedlings of rice variety PTB10 were transplanted in 10-cm-diameter earthen pots containing sterilized soil (500 g/pot). At 6 d after planting, 0, 1, 4, and 16 *Meloidogyne graminicola* egg masses/plant were introduced in the root zone. The treatments were in 8 replications in a randomized block design. Symptoms of infestation on foliage and external symptoms and gall formation on the root system were recorded.

Disease caused by the root-knot nematode affected the entire rice plant, producing damage symptoms on foliage and roots.

On the foliage, tip drying was observed at all levels of inoculum. Leaf bronzing developed from the tip downward and from the margin toward the midrib of the leaf blade. Plants were chlorotic. There was considerable distortion in leaf emergence and growth. The leaves were crinkled (Fig. 1). New tillers had reduced height. Severely

1. Symptoms on plants showing crinkled appearance of leaves.

infected plants flowered and matured early. Emerging panicles were crinkled, grain setting was poor, and chaffiness was observed in the panicles.

Characteristic knots appeared in a string on the fibrous roots (Fig. 2). Roots showed profuse development of small, slender, lateral roots, resulting in a hairy root system.

Galls were beaded, club- or spindle-shaped. In cases of heavy infection, they coalesced and formed peculiar shapes. The minimum-size galls, which appeared 4 d after inoculation, were 300-550 μm long and 150-450 μm wide. Each gall

2. a) Root system of an infected plant. b) Different shapes of galls.

was as big as 13 mm long and 2.29 mm wide after egg production. □

Detection of seedborne rice fungi by blotter method

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Seed samples of Ratna, Jaya, IR24, Pusa 2-21, Phouren, and Moirangphou that had been collected 2-3 mo after harvest were kept in polythene bags in desiccators. Glass petri dishes and semitransparent plastic petri dishes were

used. Twenty-five seeds/petri dish were plated on three 11-cm diameter circles blotter paper moistened with water. Plates were incubated 6 d in B.O.D. incubators fitted with daylight tubes. Intact growths of fungal pathogens were examined with a stereoscopic microscope. Four hundred seeds/variety were tested under the following conditions:

Temperature. 17°C, 22 °C, 27°C, and 32°C with 12 h light. Temperature had a significant effect on percentage

infection of most fungi (Table 1). Higher infection percentages of *Pyricularia oryzae*, and *Nigrospora* spp. at 22°C were detected, higher infection percentages of *Drechslera oryzae*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, and *Curvularia* spp., at 27°C.

Light. Maximum infection percentages of most fungi were detected at 12 h/d exposure to light (Table 2).

Substrate moisture. Eight to 10 ml water were optimum to detect maximum infection percentages of most

seedborne rice fungi.

pH level. Infection percentages were higher at substrate moisture at pH 5-6.

Type of container. Higher infection percentages were detected in semitransparent plastic petri dishes than in glass petri dishes.

Use of streptomycin. When 100 ppm concentration streptomycin solution was used as substrate moisture, higher infection of *D. oryzae*, *T. padwickii*, and *Phoma* spp. could be detected, but growth and detection of *P. oryzae* were

reduced.

2,4-D. Use of low concentrations 2,4-D (0.05%–0.10%) in the substrate moisture restricted root growth and facilitated detection of most of the important fungi. □

Table 1. Effect of incubation temperature on infection percentage of seedborne rice pathogens by blotter method. Imphal Pin, India.

Temperature (°C)	Infection detected (%)									
	<i>D. oryzae</i>	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>T. padwickii</i>	<i>N. oryzae</i>	<i>Curvularia</i> spp.	<i>Alternaria</i> spp.	<i>Phoma</i> spp.	<i>Fusarium dimerum</i>	<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	
17	13	8	16	12	21	2	9	11	2	
22	18	22	16	16	20	6	10	18	4	
27	18	15	20	13	21	4	10	15	2	
32	19	5	27	11	27	1	10	17	0	
CD (0.05)	4	4	4	3	5	3	ns	3	2	

Table 2. Effect of light on infection percentages of seedborne rice pathogens. Imphal Pin, India.

Light h/d	Mean infection percentage transformed into angles ^a									
	<i>D. oryzae</i>	<i>P. oryzae</i>	<i>T. padwickii</i>	<i>N. oryzae</i>	<i>Curvularia</i> spp.	<i>Alternaria</i> spp.	<i>Phoma</i> spp.	<i>F. sernitectum</i>	<i>Stemphylium</i> sp.	
0 (24 h darkness)	15.83 (7.44)	12.91 (5.0)	14.86 (6.57)	24.17	28.34 (22.53)	22.62	18.76	6.99	13.46	
4	22.38 (14.50)	16.66 (8.22)	21.26 (13.15)	26.76	33.25 (30.07)	24.03	21.06	7.60	13.45	
8	23.42 (15.80)	20.04 (11.74)	24.38 (17.04)	27.35	33.59 (30.61)	25.57	21.48	8.24	11.19	
12	24.69 (17.45)	22.68 (14.86)	26.17 (19.45)	27.66	35.73 (34.00)	27.13	21.25	8.69	11.32	
16	25.36 (18.34)	21.57 (13.51)	26.78 (20.30)	27.17	34.72 (32.43)	25.85	21.83	13.66	11.43	
20	23.75 (16.25)	21.34 (13.24)	25.66 (18.75)	27.47	33.23 (30.03)	26.46	21.60	11.91	12.83	
CD (0.05)	3.50	3.32	6.39	ns	3.81	ns	ns	ns	ns	

^aFigures in parentheses indicate values transformed back to percentages.

Cost comparison of neem oil and an insecticide against rice tungro virus (RTV)

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The potential of neem oil (NO) mixed with custard-apple oil (CAO) was evaluated in three consecutive croppings 1984-85. A 50% NO:CAO mixture in 4:1 proportion at 8 liters/ha was sprayed with an ultralow volume (ULV) applicator at weekly intervals from seedling to maximum tillering stages. The treated control was sprayed with BPMC at 0.75 kg ai/ha and the untreated control with 1.66% Teepol-water solution (emulsifier). Incidence of

Comparative RTV control, yield, and net gain in ricefields sprayed with neem oil and insecticide.^a IRRI, 1987.

Treatment	RTV (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Value of yield (\$)	cost of treatment (\$)	Net gain (value of yield less cost of treatment ^b)
<i>Jan-Apr 1984</i>					
NO:CAO	5 a	6.1 a	1068	44	1024
BPMC	4 a	6.1 a	1068	125	943
Control	7 a	5.6 a	980	12	968
<i>Jun-Oct 1984</i>					
NO:CAO	4 a	5.1 a	892	44	848
BPMC	6 ab	4.7 a	822	125	697
Control	9 b	4.6 a	805	12	793
<i>Nov 1984-Mar 1985</i>					
NO:CAO	29 a	3.1 a	542	44	498
BPMC	56 b	2.5 b	438	125	313
Control	52 b	2.3 b	402	12	390

^aAv of 4 replications/cropping season. Cost of palay = US\$0.175/kg (NFA price). NO:CAO mixture and BPMC were applied 8 times during each cropping season. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bCost of treatment includes labor and materials. Control treatment cost included labor (US\$10) and 8 pc DC batteries (US\$2) for applying 1.66% Teepol-water solution (emulsifier) using an ULV-spray applicator.